

ANNUAL PLAN

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26

ABOUT ODISSEI

ODISSEI is the National Research Infrastructure for Social Sciences with diverse components, including access to data, expertise and computing, and offers a wide range of support opportunities. The infrastructure is a collaborative consortium of 45 member organisations, including social sciences faculties in the Netherlands, public research agencies, and research institutes. Its explicit aim is to unite the social sciences and create a common, national infrastructure for research.

We maintain and develop strategic partnerships with the leading academic and research institutions in the Netherlands, including [CBS](#), [DANS](#), [eScience Center](#), [SURF](#), and [Centerdata](#).

Through these partnerships, we provide access to the ODISSEI core facilities. ODISSEI also collaborates with [CLARIAH](#) (Common Lab Research Infrastructure for the Arts and Humanities) to support various intersecting developments across the Social Science and Humanities domain.

ODISSEI was launched in 2016 and the coordination is hosted by the Erasmus School of Social and Behavioral Sciences. All ODISSEI member organisations contribute to the operational budget of ODISSEI and ensure its financial sustainability and the continuity of services. Strategic development of new facilities is financed by external grants, especially NWO's Large Scale Research Infrastructure grants. In the past, ODISSEI secured financing of over €25m through Roadmap and SSHOC-NL grants, which were awarded in this scheme.

Internationally, ODISSEI is involved in [ERICs](#) (European Research Infrastructure Consortia), which include [SHARE](#) (the Survey of Health, Ageing and Retirement in Europe) and the [European Social Survey](#). It is the current host of the [IPDLN](#) (the International Population Data Linkage Network, a worldwide network of researchers interested in data linkage).

ODISSEI IN NUMBERS

52,000

Interviews conducted by ODISSEI Surveys

16

Projects using the ODISSEI Secure Super
Computer

108

Summer School alumni

1,890

Publications

2,250,000

Minutes in the LISS panel provided for free
to researchers

1,500

Attendees at events

45

Members

5,846

Searches on the ODISSEI Portal
in the last 12 months

9,946

Datasets in the ODISSEI Portal

623

CBS Microdata Research Projects financed

MESSAGE FROM THE CHAIR

Newton was wrong: when he wrote "if I have seen further [than others], it is by standing on the shoulders of giants," he could not peek downwards past the shoulders he was standing on. If he had, he would not have seen the single expansive torso of a "great man of science", but, instead, a large tower of people of many different kinds, collaborating, competing, debating, and stretching upwards together, as far as the limited resources of each of their times allowed. Real-life science is less reminiscent of legendary Paul Bunyans, and more of real-life human pyramids such as Catalan castells (left) or Indian Dahi Handi.

ODISSEI is here to raise the platform on which Dutch social scientists stand by building world-class foundational infrastructure; to increase their reach towards new knowledge by providing both young and established researchers with skills and resources; and to advance collaboration and healthy debate through community building. In the past years, ODISSEI was highly successful in building a wide portfolio of services which are widely used across our member institutes, providing data and training to hundreds of researchers, and stimulating new collaborations and new ideas. Our honorary chair Pearl Dykstra's vision of "better infrastructure, better science, better society" has come a long way.

In 2026, our work will intensify considerably, as SSHOC-NL continues, ODISSEI receives a mandate from the SSH council to coordinate the spending of sector plan structural funds for infrastructure, and we start building the newly awarded large-scale research infrastructure MacroScope. We are very excited to start work on delivering the world's first integrated secure environment to link and analyze massive datasets spanning social, cultural and digital domains across the entire Dutch population, to understand complex societal dynamics.

The challenge will indeed be "gigantic", but fortunately we can stand on the shoulders of the amazing work that has already been delivered in the past 10 years of ODISSEI, including the OSSC, SANE, PORT data donation, SoDa, PopNet/PlanetNL, LISS, Mass Online Experiments, the Data Access Broker, the ODISSEI Portal, the data collections, and CBS's microdata access, as well as the many fantastic resources found within Clariah.

In the following pages, you will therefore find many expansions and improvements of these already-popular services, as well as a few new ones; more importantly, you will find integrations between these components, which, together, will bring the foundation for Dutch social science and humanities research up to a new level. You will also find an expansion of our community building and educational activities there, as we aim to improve the skills and resources of the next generation of social scientists and expand the use of our resources across all subdisciplines of social science.

ODISSEI is a collaborative network, built for and by the community. It therefore also includes input of new ideas from collaborations and fellowships in the social data science (SoDa) team and other projects, direct suggestions to the coordinating team at EUR, and from consultations. Several of these ideas for new infrastructure components are in the works such as the new CBS replication games, or have already been included in the task plans for 2026. Thank you all for your involvement and support.

Together, let's keep raising and strengthening this living human tower of Dutch social science, allowing researchers across the country to add new levels of knowledge, and, ultimately, improving our society.

DANIEL OBERSKI

CHAIR, ODISSEI

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GOVERNANCE

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GOVERNANCE

ODISSEI is the **Dutch National Infrastructure for Social Sciences** and provides access to a federated set of services to ODISSEI member organizations. Its explicit mission is to provide researchers with the necessary data, expertise and resources to conduct ground-breaking research and embrace the computational turn in social inquiry.

Through ODISSEI, researchers have access to large-scale, longitudinal data collections as well as **innovative and diverse new forms of data**. These can be linked to administrative data at Statistics Netherlands (CBS). Combining data from a wide range of sources enables researchers to answer new, exciting, interdisciplinary research questions and to investigate existing questions in novel, new ways.

ODISSEI now consists of **45 member organizations**. When submitting the Macroscope proposal in 2024, 31 member organisations have already committed to ODISSEI membership until 2031.

The **Supervisory Board** consists of seven members: Claes de Vreese (Deans of Social Science, chair), Susan Branje (Deans of Social Science), Maarten van Ham (Deans of Social Science), Viola Angelini (Deans of Economics), Hanneke Imbens (Statistics Netherlands), Beate Völker (KNAW/NWO institutes and E-infrastructures), and Paulette Flore (public research institutes). The supervisory board meets twice a year to approve and evaluate the infrastructures work programme.

The **Management Board** consists of eleven members: Daniel Oberski (UU, Chair), Tom Emery (EUR, Exec. Director), Dorret Boomsma (VU), Jacco van Ossenbruggen (VU), Jessica Piotrowski (UvA), Marcel Das (Centerdata), Ran van den Boom (Statistics Netherlands), Annette Langedijk (SURF), Collete Bos (NLeSC), and Anja Smit (DANS). The Management Board meets monthly to discuss and evaluate the program of work.

The **Coordination Team** is composed of Tom Emery (Exec. Director), Lucas van der Meer (Chief Technical Officer), Kasia Karpinska (Scientific Manager), Theodora Canciu (Project Manager), Evgeniia Krichever (Communications Manager) and Angelica Maineri (Data Manager). The coordination team ensures smooth, day-to-day operations of the infrastructure and implementation of the Management Boards decisions.

An **International Advisory Board** has been established, including Julia Lane (New York University), Melinda Mills (University of Oxford), Sally Wyatt (Maastricht University), Bonnie Wolff-Boenisch (CESSDA), and Amy O'Hara (Georgetown University). The board meets annually to provide guidance and advice on the strategic development of ODISSEI.

PROGRAMME OF WORK

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OVERVIEW

ODISSEI includes a wide range of activities that are integrated into a single coherent programme of work that is structured around four complimentary work streams

The Data Facility provides the foundation for secure access, linkage and analysis of sensitive data. It includes CBS Microdata Access, the ODISSEI Portal, the Secure Supercomputer and SANE. Together, these components ensure that researchers can find data, request it, process it in trusted environments and perform complex analyses that require advanced computing. This stream supplies the technical and legal backbone that everything else depends on.

The Observatory sustains and enriches the datasets researchers use, from international surveys such as ESS and SHARE to the LISS panel, historical life-course records and the Netherlands Media Corpus. It ensures continuity of high-quality data collection and introduces new forms of longitudinal, historical and multimodal data. These resources flow directly into the infrastructures of the Data Facility, where they become discoverable, linkable and analysable.

The Laboratory develops new methods and tools that expand what researchers can do with the data provided by the Observatory and managed by the Data Facility. Data donation through PORT, Mass Online Experiments and the PopNet platform all demonstrate how the Laboratory creates new forms of digital, behavioural and network data and new analytical capabilities. These innovations rely on secure computing environments and, in turn, become part of the broader data ecosystem.

The Hub connects all these elements by giving researchers the support, training and coordination needed to use the infrastructure effectively. Through governance, communication, education and the FAIR and ELSI support services, the Hub ensures that the community can navigate the increasing complexity of ODISSEI's facilities. It also translates new tools, datasets and workflows from the other streams into practical skills and guidance for users.

The underlying links between the work streams are strong and intentional. Data collected by the Observatory becomes accessible and analysable through the Data Facility. The Laboratory builds innovative methods that draw on these data and depend on secure access and computational power. The Hub then trains, supports and coordinates researchers so they can work across all streams. The entire system operates as a cycle in which data, methods, infrastructure and community reinforce each other, enabling researchers to move seamlessly from discovery to analysis to innovation.

1

DATA FACILITY

1.1

CBS Microdata Access

1.2

ODISSEI Portal

1.3

ODISSEI Secure Supercomputer

1.4

Secure Analysis Environment
(SANE)

The Data Facility supports access, linkage, and analysis of sensitive data in a safe, secure, and ethical manner.

1.1. CBS MICRODATA ACCESS

CBS Microdata Access enables researchers from ODISSEI member organisations to analyse detailed administrative and survey data in secure environments, forming the foundation for longitudinal and linked research on the Dutch population.

Task leader
Ran van den Boom (r.vandenboom@cbs.nl)

Current status

CBS Microdata Access remains the most-used facility within ODISSEI's Data stream. In 2025, almost 400 active microdata projects were conducted by 45 ODISSEI member organisations, a 12 percent increase over 2024. To facilitate access, ODISSEI re-established the 25 percent member discount on the project start-up costs and waived the €350 new-user registration fee for ODISSEI member organizations. In two rounds of the Microdata Access Grant (MAG) programme, ODISSEI awarded €95.000 to 12 projects, prioritising early-career researchers. The ODISSEI Data Storage service for secure sharing and reuse of complex (derived) datasets ingested 6 files and work is ongoing to rapidly expand this collection. A pilot for synthetic microdata was launched, bringing testing of the analytical code on the synthetic version of the data outside the secure environment a step closer to the research community. The Trusted Upload and Linking Procedure (TULP), developed with SURF, was tested on two NTR datasets to enable cross-domain data linkage and is being extended to further cohorts. CBS also deployed the App Dashboard interface for RStudio in the ODISSEI Secure Supercomputer (OSSC) and launched the self-service portal with automated billing and project-status tracking. Semi-automated ingestion of CBS metadata into the ODISSEI portal was deployed to support interoperability and data discovery, while a pilot for automatic output checks explored the possibilities for quick and secure evaluation of the research outputs. With those developments, CBS Microdata Services maintains its world-leading position in making administrative data accessible to the research community.

Challenges and future needs

Growing use creates pressure on processing capacity and a strain on support staff. Optimisation of the processes is key to mitigating those challenges while ensuring continuous access to the microdata and researcher support. An upgrade in hardware and software is needed to respond adequately to increased demand and the changing needs of the community. The synthetic-data pilot should scale while maintaining confidentiality of the data, and advancements in automatic output checks are required to shorten the output release time. Improved metadata quality and machine-actionability are needed to facilitate automated discovery through the ODISSEI Portal.

Future plans (2026)

- **Community access and support.** Continue two MAG calls (€ 95.000) and maintain both the discount and fee waiver; host quarterly training and user forums on linkage and synthetic data. Support the execution of the Replication Games for scientific papers using microdata, aiding transparency in scientific inquiry.
- **Accessibility of microdata.** Expand the data storage with new data sets and develop a conversion tool for population wide network files, making these files more accessible to researchers.
- **Synthetic data service.** Explore a synthetic-data facility to support teaching and methodological development and to reduce pre-access waiting times.
- **Automatic output checks.** Explore the possibilities of user annotation to support the output control while maintaining the disclosure standards, to cut the processing time for researchers.
- **Secure linkage and federated analysis.** Operationalise TULP for routine linkage of biomedical, survey and administrative datasets and align procedures with SURF's federated compute infrastructure for cross-domain research.
- **Hardware and software expansion.** Extend App Dashboard functionality in the ODISSEI Secure Supercomputer to Python, and upgrade compute and storage capacity in the regular CBS Microdata Environment (CBS ME) to increase the potential for parallel processing.
- **Metadata interoperability.** Launch the new metadata system with DOI assignment and automatic harvesting into the ODISSEI Portal for 2.500 datasets, to ensure improved findability of the data.

Itemised budget

Planned 2026 expenditure is **€537.045**. This includes **€108.850 from SSHOC-NL** for coordination and community support (1 FTE project liaison, training and events) and **€378.195 from the MacroScope** project to expand secure linkage and synthetic-data capabilities, and further advance the automatic disclosure checks within the federated analysis workflow. Efforts to expand the hardware and software capabilities and metadata interoperability will be covered by both financing streams. In addition, **€50.000 from ODISSEI core budget** will be allocated to the new microdata discount and free authorisation of the new researchers. These investments increase capacity, reduce onboarding times and secure CBS Microdata Access as the foundation of ODISSEI's national secure-data infrastructure.

The screenshot shows the user interface of the Statistics Netherlands (CBS) microdata portal. At the top left is the CBS logo and the text 'Statistics Netherlands'. To the right is a 'LOG IN' link. Below the logo is a navigation menu with links for 'Home', 'Questions and technical support', 'About microdata research', and 'Nederlands'. The main content area has a dark blue background with a white line graph and the text 'Good evening, welcome to CBS'. Below this is a sub-header: 'View and manage the progress of your microdata projects with Statistics Netherlands (CBS)'. There are three white buttons: 'Questions / notifications', 'Log in', and 'Request an account'. At the bottom, there is a light grey footer with the text 'Supported by' and the ODISSEI logo.

1.2. ODISSEI PORTAL

The ODISSEI Portal is the national entry point for social-science data, bringing together metadata from diverse providers so researchers can find, compare and request datasets – and increasingly connect directly to secure environments for analysis.

Task leader

Ricarda Braukmann (ricarda.braukmann@dans.knaw.nl)

Current status

In 2025, the **ODISSEI Portal** consolidated its role as the data discovery layer within ODISSEI and attracted **over 8,000 visits in the last 12 months**. Metadata from CBS, DANS, the LISS panel and additional providers are harvested, harmonised, enriched, and exposed, now covering **over 9,500 datasets**. The Individual Development Data Catalogue (CD2) was successfully integrated into the portal, containing information on varied longitudinal studies on the development of children in the Netherlands. Moreover, technical preparations have been completed for machine-actionable descriptions of access conditions so that discovery can lead directly to requests and requests to trusted analysis environments through the Data Access Broker (DAB). These activities position the Portal as the unifying interface across ODISSEI's infrastructure, a practical solution towards FAIR implementation for many data providers, and a key Dutch contribution to European-wide developments with metadata technologies. In parallel to data discovery, the ODISSEI Code Library unlocks access to a growing collection of user-generated analytical scripts to facilitate use of CBS microdata and LISS panel data to further accelerate scientific discovery. Last but not least, the ODISSEI Knowledge Graph connects various resources (e.g., data, variables, code, publications) to serve the complex needs of computational social science workflows more effectively.

Challenges and future needs

With expanding coverage, the main challenges are maintaining metadata quality at scale and ensuring interoperability across domains and providers. Automatic representation of access conditions and reliable hand-off to secure analysis environments requires close coordination with SURF and data providers. As the Portal moves from project to service phase, stable operational capacity, sustained provider engagement and alignment with European catalogues (e.g. CESSDA, EOSC) are preconditions for long-term sustainability. The Knowledge Graph needs to be improved in coverage and usability to evolve into the central gateway role envisioned for the Macroscopic project.

#	Title	Project lead	Code Language	Publication	Data used
1	Enhancing Accuracy in Country-Wide Agent-Based Epidemiological Modeling through the Application of 17 Million Individual-Level Microdata Points	Ahmad Hesam		doi	CBS microdata
2	Discontinuities in the Age-Victimisation Profile and the Determinants of Victimisation	Anna Bindler	Stata	doi	CBS microdata
3	Making Big Data Meaningful for a Promising	Anton Schreuder	R; Python	doi	CBS microdata

Future plans (2026)

- **Automated access workflows.** Integrate the Data Access Broker with the Portal so researchers can submit access requests directly from discovery pages and, for sensitive data, be handed off securely to SANE – establishing the first end-to-end workflow from dataset discovery to analysis.
- **Metadata improvements.** Onboard new data providers (e.g. ODISSEI data collections, owners of data shared via SANE); improve metadata by developing machine-actionable access and license conditions and enriching geospatial and temporal elements using controlled vocabularies; develop a data linkage framework and assessment, and embed it into metadata.
- **Knowledge-graph powered search.** Expand the coverage of the Knowledge Graph to broader SSH research, potentially connect it to the Netherlands Research Portal, and create proof-of-concepts for joint search of data, publications and code.
- **CD2 integration.** Maintain the CD2 catalogue operations and its connection to the Portal, publish CD2 FAIR controlled vocabularies and upgrade the metadata ingestion pipeline to make it more sustainable.
- **Cross-domain and European alignment.** Implement metadata export formats (e.g., DCAT-AP) needed for better connections to other domains (e.g., health sciences) and enable harvesting by European catalogues (e.g., CESSDA data catalogue) to better integrate ODISSEI into the national and international landscape.

Itemised budget

Planned 2026 expenditure is **€921.978**. This covers staff based at DANS, the VU Amsterdam, SURF, and Utrecht University. **€477.283** from SSHOC-NL for metadata improvements, and cross-domain and European alignment, **€92.935** from the Other (PDI-SSH) projects for CD2 catalogue integration, and **€351.760** from the Macroscopic project for automated discovery-to-access workflows and knowledge-graph search. These combined investments transform the Portal from a metadata registry into a fully operational gateway linking discovery, request and secure analysis across ODISSEI's national data infrastructure.

The screenshot shows the ODISSEI Portal website. At the top, there is a navigation bar with the 'Dataverse' logo on the left and links for 'Add Data', 'Search', 'User Guide', 'Support', 'English', and 'Log In' on the right. Below the navigation bar is the ODISSEI logo, which consists of a stylized blue head profile with a network of dots and lines, followed by the word 'ODISSEI' in large, bold, blue capital letters. Underneath the logo, the text 'ODISSEI Portal' and 'Discover Social Science Datasets Across The Netherlands' is displayed. A 'Metrics' section shows '0 Downloads'. There are 'Contact' and 'Share' buttons. A welcome message states: 'Welcome to the prototype of the ODISSEI portal. The ODISSEI Portal combines metadata from a wide variety of research data repositories into a single interface, allowing for advanced semantic queries to support findability, and facilitate data access. The portal is under active development and features and content will be improved throughout the ODISSEI Roadmap project. This version features a link to the Data Access Broker (DAB) through which open datasets can be downloaded directly. For restricted access datasets, the DAB links to the provider's page for more information. The link to the DAB is listed under Terms > Data Access Place for each dataset.' At the bottom, there is a carousel of logos for partner organizations: CBS, LISS, DANS (Data Archiving and Networked Services), and HSN.

1.3. ODISSEI SECURE SUPERCOMPUTER (OSSC)

The ODISSEI Secure Supercomputer provides high-performance, secure computing for sensitive data analyses, enabling workloads that exceed standard remote-access capacity.

Task leader

[Ahmad Hesam \(ahmad.hesam@surf.nl\)](mailto:ahmad.hesam@surf.nl)

Current status

In 2025, the **OSSC**, hosted by SURF on Snellius, provided trusted high-performance computing for research using CBS microdata and other secure datasets. Through the Trusted Upload and Linking Procedure (TULP), researchers linked external data sources to CBS microdata for the first time under automated compliance checks. The App Dashboard simplified use of the system, and new environments for RStudio broadened the range of supported tools. **User demand increased from 16 to 24 projects**, driven by collaboration between CBS, SURF and ODISSEI. The projects serviced by the facility are increasingly complex in terms of the methods being applied, the scope of the data being used and computational demands, testifying to the computational turn in the social sciences. This includes the first multi-GPU projects and the training of very large life course models, capable of predicting a range of life events across the whole Dutch population. The first results of the PreFer data challenge were also published which provide a benchmark for these models performance into the future.

Challenges and future needs

Scaling up usage requires further integration with SURF Research Cloud, automatic resource allocation, and improved documentation and support for users. Legal and technical agreements for linking multiple secure environments (CBS Microdata Environment, SANE, and OSSC) must be maintained and periodically reviewed. Sustaining computational capacity and securing long-term governance for high-performance secure computing will be essential as demand continues to grow.

Network determinants of upward socio-economic mobility in the Netherlands Eszter Bokanyi (Leiden University)

The POPNET project analyzes the evolution of the Dutch population's social network (2009–2022) using CBS microdata linking family, school, work, neighbour, and household ties. The dataset comprises 14 annual networks with 27 million nodes, ~2 billion edges across 33 relation types, totaling ~2 TB in 100–150 files. To study changes in degree, clustering, and distance distributions—and their relationship to income growth and educational diversity—we require high-performance computing resources. The CBS Microdata Environment (2 cores, 32 GB RAM, 100 GB disk) cannot handle the computational load. We therefore plan to use supercomputing infrastructure to (1) generate compressed, memory-efficient network representations, (2) perform large-scale matrix operations and graph-measure computations, and (3) run continuous longitudinal analyses across all years. This setup will enable scalable, reproducible computation of dynamic population-scale network metrics.

Future plans (2026)

- **Federated secure computing.** Develop the architecture for federated analysis across CBS, SANE and OSSC environments so that data can remain in place while computations occur jointly through secure pipelines, allowing researchers greater flexibility.
- **User experience and automation.** Extend the App Dashboard to Python, introduce automatic job submission and resource monitoring, and provide step-by-step onboarding documentation for researchers, which will remove the barriers for the users to interact with the high-performance compute environment and foster further uptake of the facility.
- **Training and outreach.** Organise national workshops on secure high-performance computing for social-science data, demonstrating reproducible pipelines and compliance practices.
- **Performance and capacity expansion.** Add storage and GPU capacity to Snellius nodes dedicated to ODISSEI, increasing parallel-processing power by 50 percent.
- **Governance and sustainability.** Formalise operational agreements between SURF and ODISSEI for hardware refresh, software maintenance and cost recovery to secure the OSSC as a permanent facility within the national infrastructure, to ensure the sustainability of the facility.

Itemised budget

Planned 2026 expenditure is **€411.201 from the Macroscope** project for federated-computing development and hardware expansion. These investments consolidate the OSSC as the high-performance compute core of ODISSEI's secure-data services and a key node in Europe's trusted research environment network.

1.4. SECURE ANALYSIS ENVIRONMENT (SANE)

Automated and legally compliant Secure Analysis Environments connect data providers and researcher. It brings together the Secure Analysis Environment (SANE), the Data Access Broker (DAB), and Firmbackbone (FBB) to enable access to sensitive data.

Task leader

Lucas van der Meer (lucas@odissei-data.nl)

Current status

In 2025, **SANE** transitioned from a pilot under the PDI-SSH programme to an operational service available to all ODISSEI members through SURF Research Cloud. Twenty SANE projects ran successfully. Data providers can now configure their own secure environments with pre-approved software, and Python package installation is supported via Conda. The SANE data provider portal was redesigned with easier two-factor authentication through SRAM. Agreements with eight data providers permit the analysis of sensitive datasets, and three further agreements are in preparation. Firmbackbone (FBB), an infrastructure for enriched company data that is available through SANE, expanded its data holdings with new company, employment and domain-name datasets, while its workflows for legal vetting and data onboarding were refined. Higher resolution YOUTH and LISS panel data have been made available exclusively through SANE. The Data Access Broker (DAB) achieved proof-of-concept, demonstrating machine-readable licence expressions that can pass structured requests between the ODISSEI Portal, data providers and SANE.

Challenges and future needs

Key challenges include aligning release cycles between SURF Research Cloud, DAB and SANE; maintaining the legal and technical documentation required for provider onboarding; and developing long-term funding and governance to embed these services permanently within ODISSEI. Legal and contractual arrangements for new data sources remain complex. Scaling SANE usage will depend on improving usability and automating legal workflows. FBB must expand its dataset coverage and streamline ingestion, while DAB needs to move from prototype to production status.

Future plans (2026)

- **Community engagement.** Conduct a series of workshops and targeted meetings with data providers to accelerate legal onboarding and gather feedback for future development.
- **User experience and automation.** Simplify SANE configuration for data providers and researchers, introduce automatic reporting of usage and compliance metrics, and expand helpdesk and onboarding materials.
- **Integration of SANE, DAB and FBB.** Deploy the DAB in production and connect it with the ODISSEI Portal and SANE so that access requests, licence checks and environment provisioning occur automatically. FBB will deliver new financial and company-network data and act as a key data source in this integrated workflow, which will offer a ready-to-use service for the researchers.
- **Federated secure environments.** Extend SANE to support federated analyses across institutions, enabling computation on distributed datasets without transfer of sensitive information.
- **Governance and sustainability.** Establish joint ODISSEI-SURF governance with clear cost-sharing and decision-making arrangements and define the post-project funding model for SANE and FBB.

Itemised budget

Planned 2026 expenditure is **€867.681**: **€268.235 from SSHOC-NL** for integration and development work on the Data Access Broker and coordination with SURF, **€373.868 from PDI-SSH funding for SANE** for technical development and project management at SURF and EUR, and **€225.578 from PDI-SSH funding for Firmbackbone** for data-engineering and governance activities at Utrecht University. Together, these investments establish SANE, Firmbackbone and the Data Access Broker as a unified, production-grade secure-data service embedded in ODISSEI's national infrastructure.

2

OBSERVATORY

2.1

Data Collection

2.2

Online Panels

2.3

Netherlands Media Corpus

The Observatory sustains and optimises valuable, long-standing data collections and collection and integration of new types of data.

2.1. DATA COLLECTION

ODISSEI sustains Dutch participation in key longitudinal and cross-national surveys and advances historical life-course data integration to support multi-generational research.

Task leader

Marika Knoef (M.G.Knoef@tilburguniversity.edu)

Current status

The **Data Collection Committee** is responsible for identifying data collections of key strategic interest to the Dutch research community and ensuring their continuity. In 2025, ODISSEI maintained continuity for major Dutch contributions to international surveys, including the European Social Survey (ESS), the Survey of Health, Ageing and Retirement in Europe (SHARE), the International Social Survey Programme (ISSP), the European Values Study (EVS), and the Dutch Parliamentary Study which was conducted in conjunction with the 2025 parliamentary election. Preparations began for the next ESS and SHARE waves, and coordination was strengthened between fieldwork teams and ODISSEI's FAIR and secure-data infrastructures. At the same time, the Historical Sample of the Netherlands (HSN) and other heritage-data initiatives advanced the digitisation and integration of life-course records. Collaboration between IISG, DANS and CBG (Central Bureau of Genealogy) produced protocols for scanning, optical character recognition and secure storage of over six million person cards from the Central Bureau of Genealogy archive. These efforts have reinforced ODISSEI's role as a central platform for sustaining longitudinal and historical data resources. ODISSEI also supports access to the Luxembourg Income Study (LIS) for all researchers at Dutch institutions. The data collection committee is open to the ODISSEI community and can be contacted if a strategic data concern is identified.

Challenges and future needs

A key challenge is balancing long-term funding for international survey participation with investment in new data sources. The processing of historical records must comply with strict privacy and ethical standards. Harmonising metadata across contemporary and historical sources and linking them to secure-analysis workflows will require sustained technical capacity and governance agreements. Retaining experienced fieldwork and data-collection partners is essential to maintain Dutch representation in European infrastructures.

Future plans (2026)

- **Survey participation and coordination.** Sustain Dutch involvement in ESS Round 12 and SHARE Wave 11 and support preparations for future ISSP and EVS rounds.
- **Test and Deploy Cost Saving Methods.** Led by the Data Collection Team at Utrecht University, several experiments and pilots will be launched to examine ways to collect high quality but cost efficient data across the surveys in ODISSEI.
- **Historical life-course integration.** Finalise the digitisation and cleaning of the person-card archive, produce standardised variable lists for occupation, religion and location, and prepare the first sample for secure analysis in SANE.
- **Metadata harmonisation.** Integrate survey and historical metadata into the ODISSEI Portal to enhance discoverability and enable cross-domain research.
- **Linkage and reuse.** Pilot the linkage of historical and contemporary survey data to support intergenerational research.
- **Community engagement.** Organise a national workshop on multi-generational research, aligning archival, academic and policy communities around shared infrastructure priorities.

Itemised budget

Planned 2026 expenditure is **€1.202.853**: **€223.455 from SSHOC-NL** for digitisation, metadata harmonisation and linkage of historical records and **€405.648 from the MacroScope** for survey participation and coordination. In addition to this, the International Membership Budget from NWO contributes **€500,000 towards the fielding of ESS and SHARE** and **€33.750 from ODISSEI core budget** will be allocated to TiU for the ESS coordination, and **€40.000** for the implementation of the open-source oTree software for real-time online (mass) experiments within the LISS panel. These investments secure continuity in Dutch participation in international surveys while enabling new research on long-term social and demographic change through integrated historical data.

2.2. ONLINE PANELS

ODISSEI supports access and methodological innovation for the LISS panel, integration with emerging tools, and the development of the Participant and Respondent Platform (PANL) as a next-generation facility for online data collection and participant recruitment.

Task leader

Marcel Das (marcel.das@centerdata.nl)

Current status

In 2025, the **LISS panel** remained the cornerstone of ODISSEI's data-collection infrastructure, supporting hundreds of academic and policy studies. With 7,500 active panel members from 5,000 households, the panel continues to be representative of the Dutch population. Two refreshment samples were drawn to maintain demographic balance and offset attrition. The LISS panel Grants scheme enabled ten research projects from ODISSEI member institutions to collect data at no cost. New technical capabilities were piloted: integration of the PORT data-donation framework for linking survey and digital-trace data, and the first live experiment using oTree for large-scale interactive studies. The Participant and Respondent Platform (PANL), a service that connects researchers with participants for research studies, advanced toward operational readiness with specifications for authentication, consent and data management. These developments strengthen ODISSEI's ability to support innovative, ethically compliant, and large-scale online research.

Challenges and future needs

The main challenge remains sustaining panel representativeness, reaching underrepresented groups, particularly young adults and migrant populations, whilst simultaneously expanding the panel to meet very high levels of demand from the research community. Technical and governance work is required to bring PANL into full production and to integrate it with other ODISSEI services such as SANE and the Portal. Further investment in automation, user support and participant incentives will be essential to secure long-term sustainability. Aligning questionnaire metadata and variable descriptions with FAIR standards remains an ongoing priority.

Improving Diagnosis of Memory Decline

Thomas Wilschut, Andrea Stocco, and Stephan Bakker (RUG, LISS Panel Grant)

Assessing long-term memory is vital for diagnosing and treating conditions such as Alzheimer's disease. To interpret memory abnormalities effectively, normative data from a representative Dutch sample are needed. This project uses a new computer-based test that estimates forgetting speed to evaluate long-term memory. The tool is fast, reliable, and repeatable, but prior studies involved only highly educated participants. We will now examine how memory performance varies with age, education, and socio-economic status, providing benchmarks for diagnostic use and insights into how environmental factors shape memory function.

Future plans (2026)

- **LISS panel maintenance and refreshment.** Conduct a refreshment sample focused on underrepresented groups to maintain population coverage and representativeness.
- **Participant and Respondent Platform (PANL).** Finalise technical implementation and governance, launch the first production cycle, and begin onboarding research groups. PANL will provide the basis for future large-scale online and hybrid studies within ODISSEI.
- **Methodological innovation.** Expand the integration between LISS, PORT and secure computing environments to enable studies combining self-reported and behavioural data. Invest in the development of the LISS mobile app to leverage the response rate, access mobile sensor data, and promote an even more efficient connection between the integrated online data collection infrastructure.
- **Open calls and community engagement.** Continue the LISS panel Grants scheme for ODISSEI members and deliver training on experimental and mixed-method designs, to facilitate access to the facility for the research community.
- **Metadata and interoperability.** Implement improved variable-level metadata following FAIR standards and publish documentation through the ODISSEI Portal.

Itemised budget

Planned 2026 expenditure is **€1.140.410**: **€250.000 from SSHOC-NL** for LISS panel operations and refreshment sampling, and **€674.000 from the Macroscope** for the integration of behavioural and survey data collection. In addition, **€216.410 PDI-SSH funding for PANL** will advance the operational readiness of this facility. These combined resources ensure the long-term sustainability of the LISS infrastructure and expand ODISSEI's capacity for innovative online and hybrid research designs.

2.3. NETHERLANDS MEDIA CORPUS

The Netherlands Media Corpus (NMC) will enable researchers to analyse large-scale media collections—textual, audiovisual and online—in interoperable, standards-based environments. In the Macroscopic project, the Netherlands Media Corpus will develop the Analytical Toolbox to support reproducible, AI-assisted media research.

Task leader

Jessica Pietrowski (J.Piotrowski@uva.nl)

Current status

The **Netherlands Media Corpus (NMC)** is a new element of the collaboration between ODISSEI and CLARIAH that will bring together a heterogeneous collection of media data, spanning text, audiovisual and born-digital formats, with advanced AI tools supporting annotation, processing, management and FAIRification tasks. NMC integrates data from various sources, from traditional archives to evolving social media platforms, and will be designed and implemented jointly by ODISSEI (UvA) and CLARIAH (KB). Developed under Macroscopic, the NMC builds on existing work.

Within the Roadmap project, the Media Content Analysis Lab (MCAL) established the foundations for a national infrastructure for digital media analysis. It produced the MCALentory, an annotated inventory of almost 200 research papers capturing information about research questions, content-analysis methods, and data availability. Made available in the form of a knowledge graph, this inventory supports replication, meta-analysis and methodological innovation in communication research, and will be seamlessly integrated into the NMC. The MCALentory knowledge graph also provided a proof-of-concept for making media-analysis resources FAIR. Within SSHOC-NL, CLARIAH Media Suite is made more interoperable with ODISSEI's ecosystem (i.e., SANE, DAB). This collaboration prepares the technical groundwork for integrating media data from CLARIAH and ODISSEI into the NMC. With Macroscopic, the Netherlands Media Corpus and the Analytical Toolbox take media analysis to the next level, empowering SSH researchers to link and analyse media data from diverse sources in a collaborative, dynamic ecosystem.

Challenges and future needs

The major challenge for the NMC is ensuring that heterogeneous data—from broadcast archives to social media platforms—remains interoperable and reusable. Aligning metadata models and licences across data providers requires negotiation and technical coordination. Sustaining developer capacity for the Analytical Toolbox and providing sufficient computing resources for deep-learning applications are critical for meeting research demand. To foster widespread adoption, NMC must strengthen documentation, user support and training.

Future plans (2026)

- **Netherlands Media Corpus.** Set up shared guidelines for large-scale ingestion and processing of textual, audiovisual and web materials from KB, Beeld en Geluid and other partners holding media data; prepare the longitudinal collection of web and media diets from LISS panel respondents.
- **Analytical Toolbox.** Define the roadmap towards a release of the Toolbox containing modules for automatic speech recognition, visual object detection, sentiment and topic analysis, and multimodal alignment. Also include the integration of these components into the SURF Research Cloud and provision APIs for reproducible workflows.
- **Interoperability and metadata.** Register media datasets in the ODISSEI Portal for discoverability and FAIRification, including persistent identifiers for all curated collections; align media collections' metadata schemas with Macroscopic Knowledge Graph requirements to make resources findable and linkable through it.
- **User support and training.** Develop detailed documentation, tutorials and open-source examples; organise workshops and training events to build the community of practice around media data analysis.
- **Ethics and compliance.** Update legal frameworks and consent procedures for the reuse of online and audiovisual materials, to ensure alignment with national and European privacy regulations.

Itemised budget

Planned 2026 expenditure is **€504.672** from the Macroscopic project: combining **€339.764** for continued development of the Netherlands Media Corpus and **€ 164.908** for completion and deployment of the Analytical Toolbox at UvA and the KB. These investments deliver a fully operational national facility to enable media analysis, giving researchers secure, scalable access to multimodal media and web data and state-of-the-art tools for automated annotation and interpretation.

3

LABORATORY

3.1

Data Donation

3.2

Mass Online Experiments

3.3

Large Network Tools

The Laboratory opens up new avenues of scientific inquiry by exploiting innovative digital technologies.

3.1. DATA DONATION

Locally developed software called 'PORT' enables privacy-preserving data donation studies by providing configurable workflows, extraction scripts and guidance – linking donation to secure analysis and responsible reuse.

Task leader

Laura Boeschoten (L.boeschoten@uu.nl)

Current status

In 2025, the PORT software for **Data Donation** matured into an operational service that allows researchers to collect digital-trace data from participants in a transparent and legally compliant manner. The framework was successfully used in several donation studies within ODISSEI member organisations and integrated into the LISS panel for combined survey-donation research. This included an open call to use the software in the LISS panel for free as part of the standard LISS panel Grant process. Work continued on embedding PORT within SURF Research Cloud, enabling secure data processing for sensitive donations, and on standardising consent procedures and legal templates. Collaboration with the PDI-SSH funded D3I infrastructure strengthened the technical base for long-term sustainability and integration with secure data workflows. Together, these developments made PORT a functional and scalable component of ODISSEI's infrastructure for responsible use of digital-trace data.

Challenges and future needs

The primary challenge is consolidating PORT's service model and ensuring sustainable hosting and maintenance. Researchers require more standardised and validated extraction scripts and enhanced guidance on compliance with data-protection requirements. Integrating PORT outputs with secure analysis environments and data archives will be essential for facilitating reuse and reproducibility. Effective lobbying of data platforms is also required to ensure compliance with legislation upon which the platform depends.

Future plans (2026)

- **Service consolidation and hosting.** Establish PORT as a permanent national service with stable hosting and maintenance through SURF, ensuring long-term availability.
- **Tool integration.** Expand PORT's library of validated extraction scripts and standard connectors to widely used platforms that streamline researcher workflows.
- **Legal and ethical compliance.** Finalise and publish reusable consent templates, privacy statements and risk-assessment guidelines in collaboration with the ELSI helpdesk.
- **Reuse and linkage.** Implement secure transfer of donated datasets to trusted analysis environments for approved reuse, supported by machine-readable metadata and access conditions.
- **Community and training.** Offer regular workshops for researchers and data stewards on the design, execution and reuse of data donation studies.

Itemised budget

Planned 2026 expenditure is **€740.308**: **€141.087 from SSHOC-NL** for core PORT operations, maintenance and researcher liaison at Utrecht University, and **€244.908 from the Macroscope project** and **PDI-SSH funding of €354.313 for D3I** for expansion of the service, integration of D3I infrastructure and automation of secure data transfer. This latter work is conducted by Utrecht University and the Amsterdam School of Communication Research. They include €80,000 for the development of PORT by EYRA, a third party developer specialized in software for Science. These investments establish PORT as a sustainable and widely accessible national service for privacy-preserving data donation and responsible reuse of digital-trace data.

Fig. 1: Port Software: Step-by-step illustration of the workflow that allows for a privacy-preserving analysis of data download package

3.2. MASS ONLINE EXPERIMENTS

Mass Online Experiments are large-scale behavioural experiments run online. ODISSEI offers recruitment pathways, reusable code, technical support and hosted environments for interactive studies at national scale.

Task leader

Rense Corten (r.corten@uu.nl)

Current status

In 2025, the **Mass Online Experiments (MOE)** facility expanded its infrastructure to enable large-scale interactive experiments involving hundreds or thousands of participants. A hosted environment on SURF Research Cloud provided the technical base for experiments run with oTree and Empirica, and integration with the LISS panel and PANL allowed the recruitment of representative participant samples. Two pilot studies tested scalability and latency, demonstrating the feasibility of synchronous, multi-user experiments in real time. Collaboration with the eScience Center supported optimisation of code templates and development of an onboarding workflow for new researchers. Once operational, the platform will enable researchers to conduct highly powerful and state of the art experiments using samples that are linkable to the LISS panel, CBS microdata, and data donation studies, making ODISSEI a globally unique infrastructure. The facility also began defining a support model for long-term hosting and maintenance.

Challenges and future needs

The main challenges are finalising the governance and sustainability model for the facility and consolidating user support and documentation. Researchers require a well-defined onboarding process and examples of validated experiment templates to reduce technical barriers. Scaling up adoption will depend on increased outreach and alignment with other ODISSEI services such as PORT and PANL.

Fig. 2 Realtime user ratings as a strategy for combatting misinformation: an experimental study, by J. Stein et al, 2023.

Future plans (2026)

- **Demonstration studies.** Conduct further large-scale demonstration experiments to validate system stability and provide benchmarks for throughput and response times.
- **Template library.** Publish a repository of validated experiment templates for standard designs (coordination games, opinion dynamics, information diffusion) to promote reuse and reproducibility.
- **User onboarding and support.** Establish a helpdesk and comprehensive documentation to guide researchers in designing, deploying and analysing online experiments.
- **Community building.** Organise training sessions and outreach events to expand the user community and foster interdisciplinary collaboration. This is in preparation for calls for use of the platform in 2027.
- **Infrastructure consolidation.** Finalise the architecture for large-scale online experiments on SURF Research Cloud, enabling consistent deployment and monitoring.

Itemised budget

Planned 2026 expenditure is **€173.060 from SSHOC-NL**, covering the design of experiments and templates, participant incentives, software development and hosting at Utrecht University. These investments ensure that the Mass Online Experiments facility becomes a stable and user-friendly platform for large-scale behavioural research across disciplines. In 2027, the platform will be operational and open, competitive calls will be made for use by the ODISSEI community.

3.3. LARGE NETWORK TOOLS

PLANET-NL develops methods and tools for analyzing and using large-scale network data, enabling secure linkage, interoperability and analysis across registers and digital traces.

Task leader

Frank Takes (takes@liacs.nl)

Current status

In 2025, the Platform for **Large Network Tools** (PLANET-NL) matured from a technical pilot into an operational facility supporting researchers who analyse population-scale social networks derived from administrative and digital-trace data. The project delivered an updated prototype of the PopNet platform, integrating modules for network construction, anonymisation and disclosure-risk analysis. Algorithms for dynamic and temporal networks were implemented and tested on CBS microdata within secure environments. Collaboration between CBS, Leiden University, the University of Amsterdam and SURF produced standardised workflows for creating privacy-preserving network representations. Documentation and tutorials were drafted, and the team organised three training events with more than 150 participants from Dutch universities and government institutes. The facility's visibility increased through conference presentations and publications, establishing PopNet as the national point of reference for secure, network-based population studies.

Challenges and future needs

Scaling up to full-population coverage requires additional computing capacity and automation for disclosure control. Ensuring interoperability between network data formats, metadata standards and trusted environments is still technically complex. Broader community uptake depends on consolidating documentation, long-term maintenance of the software stack and user support. Another challenge is to formalise collaboration with CBS and other data providers so that recurrent updates of register-based networks can be delivered sustainably.

Future plans (2026)

- **Capacity and training.** Deliver at least four hands-on training events and a national summer workshop on population-scale network analytics, targeting 200 researchers and data stewards.
- **Expand Usage.** Increase direct hands on usage of the platform and monitor user engagement of the facility through the CBS Microdata Environment.
- **Software and method development.** Release new versions of network-analysis and risk-assessment tools with improved scalability and visualisation; publish open documentation and reproducible examples.
- **Secure workflows.** Integrate PopNet analysis pipelines into ODISSEI's secure environments (SANE and OSSC) to allow controlled access to sensitive network data.
- **Data and interoperability.** Define and adopt metadata standards for network datasets, coordinate with the ODISSEI Portal and DANS for registration and harvesting, and implement persistent identifiers for derived network objects.
- **International alignment.** Host an international expert meeting to align methods with European partners and contribute Dutch developments to the EOSC cluster on social-network data.
- **Sustainability and governance.** Formalise agreements with CBS and SURF for the continued production and safe dissemination of network datasets, embedding PopNet within ODISSEI's long-term secure-data strategy.

Itemised budget

Planned 2026 expenditure is **€585.175: €232.526 from SSHOC-NL** for continued development, staffing and community support, and **€126.852 from the Macroscope project** for integrating new analytical components into secure environments. In addition PopNet will receive **€225.797 under the sector plan** arrangements stemming from PDI-SSH projects which will be used to finance the core operations of PopNet. The development of PLANET-NL is conducted jointly by UvA and Leiden University and consists principally of staffing for software development as well as the costs of Microdata Access at Statistics Netherlands. These investments make PopNet a durable, privacy-aware infrastructure for analysing the connected structures underlying Dutch population data

4

HUB

4.1

Coordination

4.2

Education

4.3

Support

The Hub creates a community of infrastructure users and offers the researchers the necessary support for complex and comprehensive modelling of social phenomena.

4.1. COORDINATION

ODISSEI Coordination Team provides coordination to ensure strategic alignment, quality control, governance support and effective community engagement across the infrastructure.

Task leader

Kasia Karpinska (kasia@odissei-data.nl)

Current status

In 2025, the Coordination Team maintained daily management and communication across ODISSEI's rapidly expanding infrastructure. Regular meetings of the Supervisory Board, Management Board and Project Board ensured alignment between funding streams (SSHOC-NL and PDI-SSH). The team handled financial and technical reporting to NWO, oversaw risk management and coordinated ODISSEI's presence on the European and International scene, as well as EOSC activities. Communication efforts included the annual ODISSEI Conference with over 400 participants, monthly newsletters and active digital presence via a website, growing social media engagement and new content formats, such as the ODISSEI Podcast series. These activities kept the community informed and involved as ODISSEI moved into its €10 million operational year.

Challenges and future needs

As ODISSEI's operations grow, the complexity of coordination increases. Ensuring coherence between multiple funding sources, harmonising reporting requirements and preventing duplication across partners requires dedicated administrative capacity and robust governance procedures. Sustained effort is needed to balance strategic oversight with efficient day-to-day operations and to maintain transparency for all stakeholders. Growing operations of ODISSEI also mean more opportunities for the community to get involved in multiple ways, which bring inherent difficulties for the community to navigate ODISSEI's rich ecosystem. Engaging users requires expansion of the communication channels and delivering targeted content to meet the needs of the community.

Future plans (2026)

- **Governance and reporting.** Provide administrative and strategic support to all ODISSEI Boards and ensure timely financial and technical reporting to NWO and partners.
- **Programme integration.** Coordinate cross-stream activities and monitor interdependencies between the Data, Observatory, Laboratory and Hub workstreams.
- **Communication.** Expand communication channels through a user-focused marketing strategy that shifts from infrastructure-focused messaging to content that showcases real researchers' needs and experiences.
- **Events.** Host offline events and at least six thematic workshops, alongside major events like ODISSEI Conference, Summer School and International Population Data Linkage Network Conference (which ODISSEI hosts in 2026) to strengthen community connections. Grow awareness beyond the existing community through paid social media campaigns and targeted outreach.
- **International collaboration.** Represent ODISSEI in international consortia and EOSC networks and align national developments with European policy frameworks. Organise the International Population Data Linkage Network Conference in July 2026.
- **Monitoring and risk management.** Update the risk register and coordinate annual quality reviews for all tasks.
- **Sustainability planning.** Prepare the post-2026 governance proposal and business model for ODISSEI as a permanent national infrastructure.

Itemised budget

Planned 2026 expenditure is **€791.486**: **€459.726 from SSHOC-NL** for project and communication management and **€331.760 from the Macroscope project** for cross-infrastructure coordination and shared reporting activities. All coordination activities are conducted by the Coordination Team at Erasmus University Rotterdam. This includes a full-time team of six and material resources to cover the costs of conferences and event hosting. These resources ensure coherent governance and transparent communication across ODISSEI's expanded portfolio.

4.2. EDUCATION

ODISSEI delivers coordinated training, linking researchers to data, tools and methods across the infrastructure.

Task leader

Kasia Karpinska (kasia@odissei-data.nl)

Current status

In 2025, the education activities provided a wide range of training for researchers and data professionals. **ODISSEI SICSS Summer School** focused on using the ODISSEI infrastructure and applying complex methods of data analysis to company data (Firmbackbone data), utilising the Secure Analysis Environment (SANE), offering in-depth training to 21 early career scholars. Workshops and a series of online tutorials and blogs covered topics from secure data analysis and machine learning to metadata standardisation and FAIR implementation.

Challenges and future needs

As the infrastructure expands, training demand outpaces capacity. Developing and Embedding modules in graduate schools and university curricula is essential for sustainability. Improved tracking of participation and impact will strengthen quality assurance and reporting. These training activities will be for a range of seniority levels, emphasizing PhD's and Early Career Researchers but also up-skilling senior researchers.

Future plans (2026)

- **Training delivery.** Run ODISSEI SICSS Summer School and 4 workshops on secure computing, FAIR data and computational methods (especially—high in demand—Large Language Models in social sciences); update and expand online tutorials.
- **Integration and sustainability.** Collaborate with graduate schools and competence centres to embed training modules in existing programmes, to ensure uptake and long-term sustainability.
- **Develop New Courses** Develop new modules on basics of data science and computational methods to be made available to all member organization graduate schools.
- **International coordination.** Represent ODISSEI in European training initiatives to align national practice with international standards. Ensure ODISSEI-led workshops on analysing linked data and working in secure environments offered by ODISSEI are delivered at the IPDLN conference organised in 2026.
- **Impact and assessment.** Implement tracking of training outcomes and participant feedback for continuous improvement and a better understanding of users' needs.

Itemised budget

Planned 2026 expenditure is **€543.746**: **€186.894 from SSHOC-NL** for training delivery and coordination, and **€296.852 from the Macroscope project** for outreach and educational integration. A further **€60,000 comes from the ODISSEI Core budget** to provide training, workshops and dissemination for the ASReview software. These investments ensure that training expands in step with ODISSEI's infrastructure. The costs of the Educational programme are administered by Erasmus University Rotterdam and are principally the material costs associated with operating training events and programs.

4.3. SUPPORT

Support bridges researchers and infrastructure through fellowships, expert consultations, practical guidance and an ethical-legal-social (ELSI) help desk.

Task leader

Kasia Karpinska (kasia@odissei-data.nl)

Current status

In 2025, the Support programme strengthened user services for researchers working with the ODISSEI infrastructure. The SoDa Fellowships funded 3 researchers to develop reusable code, datasets and tutorials. The ELSI helpdesk pilot handled 22 requests on data-protection and AI ethics, and a new ticket system was implemented for tracking inquiries. The FAIR Expertise Hub, which started as a PDI-SSH funded project and is now a stable facility at ODISSEI, onboarded data providers to make data available via ODISSEI, consulted various projects on their FAIRification strategies, and organised two workshops around FAIR implementation. Support staff coordinated closely with SURF and the FAIR Expertise Hub to align advice on legal and technical aspects of data management. Complex, large-scale projects, such as National Groeifonds funded Meer Uren werkt! (MUW), are offered practical support in accessing the infrastructure that elevates successful project execution.

Challenges and future needs

Growing use of ODISSEI services creates higher demand for timely, specialised support. Sustaining the fellowship schemes and helpdesk requires stable funding and integration with national support networks. Expanding expertise on secure data analysis and AI-driven methods is critical to meeting community needs. FAIR support must stay aligned with European initiatives while responding to rapid technological change. Navigating ethical, legal, and social implications of research requires more integration in the social science research practice.

Future plans (2026)

- **Fellowships and mentoring.** Run a new round of fellowship grants for (social sciences and related domains) projects using ODISSEI tools; extend mentoring and publication support for fellows.
- **Create a PhD Network.** Establish and coordinate a PhD Network to represent the needs and activities of the ODISSEI PhD community.
- **Training and knowledge transfer.** Translate fellowship outputs into training materials, tutorials and code examples for wider reuse.
- **Helpdesk and user onboarding.** Operate a coordinated helpdesk for legal and ethical questions; publish an online knowledge base and templates for common issues.
- **Collaboration and alignment.** Work with national ELSI and FAIR networks to provide consistent guidance and referral mechanisms.
- **Community development.** Host biannual support forums and user meetings to gather feedback and identify emerging needs.
- **FAIR Expertise Hub.** Consolidate the Hub as a service for data providers and research groups; publish guidelines and controlled vocabularies for interoperability and metadata management.
- **Support research projects.** Offer practical support for complex projects that require multiple ODISSEI facilities, and create onboarding materials for successful access and implementation of the projects.

Itemised budget

Planned 2026 expenditure is **€938.718**: **€255.466 from SSHOC-NL** for core support coordination and fellowships to be coordinated by the SoDA Team at Utrecht University, and **€114.167 from the Macroscopic project** for gateway and community-support activities. There is a further **€226.316 from PDI-SSH for the FAIR Expertise Hub** operations and guideline development which is led by the Erasmus University Rotterdam. In addition, **€242.769 from MUW** will be allocated to the coordination of this large-scale project's infrastructure needs by Erasmus University Rotterdam and access to relevant ODISSEI facilities. Finally, €100,000 will be allocated from the ODISSEI Core Budget to Utrecht University to reinforce the support offered by SoDA and boost capacity for its much demanded services. These investments together provide a comprehensive, integrated support system that helps researchers work securely and efficiently with ODISSEI facilities.

FINANCIAL PLAN 2026

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FINANCIAL PLAN 2026

Table 1 below represents the planned expenditures for 2026 and includes multiple projects in which ODISSEI will be engaged through this period. Because ODISSEI is an infrastructure and not a collection of unrelated projects, core tasks have been identified which are identifiable within ODISSEI.

These are the tasks that structure section 3 of the Annual Plan, and Table 1 below illustrates the planned expenditure for these activities in 2026 and from which project they will be financed. The ODISSEI Coordination Team works closely with service providers to ensure continuity and coordination between projects to avoid duplication and realise efficiencies in implementation.

The task marked 'CLARIAH' represents activities within SSHOC-NL and Macroscope which are dominated by CLARIAH and whose ODISSEI involvement is limited. The majority of tasks in these projects are collaborative but a small number concentrate on key investments in the respective ODISSEI and CLARIAH communities.

Due to new project acquisitions and structural funding, 2026 will represent a 64% increase in spending for ODISSEI with a number of new initiatives. ODISSEI also retains €674,000 in unallocated reserves which it will use to address strategic opportunities as they arise. These are currently above the target of 5% of operating costs and ODISSEI aims to reduce these reserves through 2026.

Table 1 – Budgeted Revenue & Expenditure for 2026 (2024 and 2025 included as reference) [€k]

ODISSEI Tasks	Stream	2024	2025	2026
CBS	Data Facility	624	441	537
Portal	Data Facility	481	558	922
OSSC	Data Facility	254	220	411
SANE	Data Facility	834	579	868
Data Collection	Observatory	599	1195	1203
Online Panels	Observatory	758	250	1140
Netherlands Media Corpus	Observatory	81		505
Data Donation	Laboratory	20	191	740
Mass Online Experiments	Laboratory	60	170	173
Large Network Tools	Laboratory	0	228	585
Coordination	Hub	746	621	791
Education	Hub	159	184	544
Support	Hub	776	925	939
CLARIAH		198	622	989
Total		5589	6184	10347
Revenues				
Unearmarked Revenues		887	685	155
Unearmarked and Allocated Revenues		0	1053	34
Remaining Unallocated Revenues		887	-368	121
Cumulative Unallocated Revenues		887	519	640
Structural Funding		1627	1,428	2,807
Ongoing Funding		4848	5,441	7,695
Structural Funding as %		25.13%	20.79%	26.73%

KEY PERFORMANCE INDICATORS

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KEY PERFORMANCE INDICATORS

ODISSEI maintains a register of Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) that have been in place since the original ODISSEI Roadmap project and were most recently updated in October 2025, in alignment with the SSHOC-NL project and the Macroscope project award. Each year, the status of each KPI is reviewed, and new targets are set. The KPIs are proposed by the Coordination Team and Management Board, and subsequently amended and approved by the ODISSEI Supervisory Board, ensuring continuity and alignment with the project's specific and measurable objectives.

Table 2 – Key Performance Indicators 2025-2029

Indicator	Target	Current
Governance & Strategy		
Participation in international projects and infra collaborations	Direct participation in at least five international level project by 2029	TRELISS, IPDLN (+ infra collaborations: direct participation in SoBigDataEurope)
Facility Usage		
Percentage of ODISSEI member organisations being granted a project	Provide access to 50% of ODISSEI member organisations by 2030	Currently 38% of organisations have received a grant
Number of unique visitors to the ODISSEI Portal	500 unique visitors per month by 2029	On average, 414 unique visitors per month in 2025 (+13% from 2024)
Number of OSSC Projects per year	30 active projects by 2029	20 active projects
Number of projects spanning more than 2 facilities	50 per year by 2029	28 projects
Number of projects supported by Social Data Analytics Team (SoDa)	100 projects completed before end of 2029	45 projects
Number of researchers supported by Social Data Analytics Team (SoDa)	No current target set	140
Financial		
Unearmarked Revenues	No more than 5% of operating costs	3.77%
Structural Funding as %	33%	20.79%
Training & Education		
Number of attendees at training events and workshops	250 unique attendees at training events per year	115 participants in 2025
Percentage of faculties using the educational programme	75% of faculties using the educational programme	50%

Scientific Impact		
Number of scientific papers describing the infrastructure	20 by 2029	9 since 2020
Number of peer-reviewed publications derived from ODISSEI supported research projects	30 per year by 2029	15 (Jan-Oct 2025)
Number of citations received for publications derived from ODISSEI supported research projects	200 per year by 2029	131 (Jan-Oct 2025)
Communication		
ODISSEI Conference attendance	350-450 total participants	400 attendees in 2024, 2025 will be reported in 2026
LinkedIn community growth	15-20% YoY	36%
Website active users	20% YoY	66.7% - 19k by October 2025
Number of website views	25% YoY	24.4% - 74k by October 2025
Number of all-time downloads of the ODISSEI Podcast	500 by 2027	219 in 2025
Newsletter open rate	30-35%	45-50%
LinkedIn total impressions	50.000-65.000/year	570.177 in 2025
Attracting & Retaining New Talent		
Number of international scientists using ODISSEI	50 by the end of 2029	28
Retention of coordination staff	100% retention YoY	100%
Sustainability & Environmental		
Carbon footprint on HPC usage	Reporting of annual carbon footprint based on SSH HPC usage at SURF	TBD

RISK REGISTER

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RISK REGISTER

The ODISSEI Risk register is designed to support the strategic planning and decision making of the Coordination Team, the Management Board, and the Supervisory Board. Risk assessments are always subjective but consolidating the risk assessments into a singular document can help identify common risks, differences in risk perceptions across the project and interdependent mitigation strategies. The full risk register appears at the end of this document and has been used to create an overview of the various challenges faced by ODISSEI.

The high probability, high impact risks for this year were identified by Task Leaders, the Coordination Team and the Management Board and listed in Table 3. All the risks have been explicitly discussed by the Management Board and are being actively monitored by Task Leaders and Coordination Team contacts.

Table 3 – Full Risk Register

Task	#	Risk	Prob	Imp	Mitigating Action	Risk Area
Data Facility						
1.1	1	Restrictions in the usage of CBS microdata, e.g., as a follow-up of the external investigation into the security of Microdata Services	1	3	Increase technical and procedural safety warrants so that the research process itself is not affected more than necessary	Legal
1.1	2	Increased usage and costs of the discount and free waiver for authorising new researchers	1	2	The usage is monitored quarterly and the mitigating actions will be proposed when the usage will show high demand.	High Demand
1.1	3	Unequal usage of the financial schemes across scientific domains and categories of users	2	1	Monitoring of the usage, and promotion of the programmes across organisations with lower uptake.	Low Demand
1.1	4	Disclosure risk following the unlawful use of the synthetic data	1	3	Agree common protocols with CBS and arrange evaluation of synthetic data	Legal
1.1	5	Demand exceeding the capacity of the CBS Microdata Environment, leading to service outage	1	2	Exploring the scalability of the technical infrastructure and automating various parts of the infrastructure.	High Demand
1.2	1	Not being able to hire and retain appropriate staff	3	2	Widely setting out vacancies, possibility to outsource some positions.	Staffing
1.2	2	Strategic or technical misalignment between the partners	2	2	Bi-weekly, low-profile steering group and technical meetings	Coordination
1.2	3	Potential metadata providers not willing to or able to share metadata, or to invest in altering metadata	2	2	Representatives in the ODISSEI Management Board. Support and money available.	FAIR
1.2	4	Insufficient need for the Portal	1	2	Usage is monitored regularly, communications efforts ongoing	Low Demand
1.2	5	Lack of commitment for long term sustainability	1	3	DANS committed to sustain the built infrastructure for at least five years.	Sustainability
1.2	6	Insufficient knowledge and consensus on explicit semantics of social-science metadata to develop a search interface with sufficient added value for social science researchers	2	2	Make use of existing standardisation efforts in the community, including the CESSDA metadata models and thesauri.	FAIR

1.2	7	Insufficient progress in development of the Knowledge Graph	2	3	Appointed product owner within the CT and active monitoring by MB	Coordination
1.2	8	Insufficient integration the metadata from different domains into one system	3	2	Shared metadata standards, bi-weekly alignment, shared proof-of-concepts, and project board oversight	Technical
1.3	1	Misalignment between SURF and CBS	2	2	The team will have periodic meetings to ensure alignment	Coordination
1.3	2	Financial sustainability of the OSSC services	3	2	A SURF-ODISSEI sustainability strategy will be developed.	Coordination
1.3	3	OSSC interface difficult to use	2	2	Working on a graphic interface, education (Education task), developing better onboarding documentation	Technical
1.3	4	Legal and technical agreements for TULP take too long to deliver	3	2	Payment for additional legal support and coordinator of use case hired at UU	Legal
1.4	1	Interest from research community in the use of SANE is limited	2	2	Invest more effort in advertising, prepare better onboarding documents, and more data available.	Low Demand
1.4	2	Implementation from data providers is limited	1	2	Improve usability and automate legal workflows, maintain the legal and technical documentation required for provider onboarding	Low Demand
1.4	3	Technical alignment with SURF-based infrastructure (SURF Research Cloud, DAB and SANE)	2	2	SANE Governance Structure and move to Data Management Team at SURF	Technical
2.1	1	High non-response in online data collections	3	2	Knowledge exchange and shared results of online data collection	Technical
2.1	2	No further funding for data collections	1	2	The financing strategy must identify cost reduction measures and a new financing strategy and stimulate the respective survey communities to collaborate on funding applications	Sustainability
2.1	3	Linkage with the historical records is not successful	3	2	Pivot to technical solutions for security and pre-existing linkage initiatives	Legal
2.2	1	Interest in ODISSEI LISS Calls is overwhelming, leading to very low award rate and lack of capacity for experimental tools	2	2	Make calls more thematically focused; merge funds for two calls; limit the target population to e.g. early career researchers only	High Demand
2.2	2	Attrition LISS panel is non-random making the panel less representative of the Dutch (speaking) population	3	2	Intensify panel care; correct for biases with stratified refreshment samples; increase efforts to minimise attrition; if needed reallocate budget to fund additional refreshment samples	Technical
2.2	3	Response rates decrease in monthly questionnaires and experiments fielded in the LISS panel	2	2	Motivate respondents to participate using response-enhancing measures, e.g. attractiveness of questionnaires and experiments, higher monetary incentives	Technical
2.2	4	PANL does not reach production status	3	1	Extensive support and onboarding for the CT of PANL	Technical
2.2	5	Long term sustainability of the integrated data collection facility	2	3	Invest in automation, user support and participant incentives	Technical

2.3	1	NMC not embedded in wider ODISSEI community	2	2	Ensure regular contact between NMC team and wider ODISSEI Tasks	Coordination
2.3	2	Shifting investment and user requirements	3	2	The media analysis landscape is very dynamic, and an agile approach is therefore being adopted for its development	Coordination
2.3	3	Misalignment of metadata models and licences across different data sources	3	2	Invest in interoperability and reusability of all data sources	Technical
2.3	4	Limited interest from the scientific community	1	2	Invest in documentation, user support and training, ensure sufficient computational resources for researchers to conduct deep learning applications.	Low Demand
3.1	1	Scarcity of IT personnel and development companies	2	2	Continuing work with partners with whom we have positive experience and form a group of all researchers who can learn from each other's work and form a safety net in case someone (temporarily) leaves.	Staffing
3.1	2	Lack of sustainable PORT's service model	2	1	Focus on Financial Sustainability	Financial
3.1	3	Service is too complex for the users to interact with	2	2	Develop standardised and validated extraction scripts and enhanced guidance on compliance with data-protection requirements.	Technical
3.1	4	Fluid legal and technical framework for access to Very Large Online Platforms	3	2	Collaboration and alignment with key stakeholders and actors	Legal
3.2	1	Limited reusability of building blocks	2	3	Start with relatively simple experiments using common design features; introduce more specific features later.	Technical
3.2	2	Limited sustainability of support	3	3	Develop open-source with careful documentation to keep developed code accessible. Host support at a robust and committed organisation.	Sustainability
3.2	3	Lack of uptake by broader research community	1	3	Promote the project widely, using the project website, conferences, and newsletters, organise a dedicated call to use the facility free of charge.	Low Demand
3.2	4	Insufficient technical expertise of potential users	2	2	Develop an onboarding process and provide examples of validated experiment templates to reduce technical barriers	Technical
3.3	1	Difficulty in attracting sufficient talent due to tight job market	2	2	Dissemination of job ads of the first open positions through as many relevant channels as possible, making use of both scientific and research infrastructure "networks of" contacts of the task leaders.	Staffing
3.3	2	Insufficient uptake by the community	2	2	Consolidate documentation, provide long-term maintenance of the software stack and user support, develop tools for improved access.	Low Demand

3.3	3	Lack of clear service model for users and technical integration	2	3	Alignment and collaboration with CBS, SURF and potential user community	Coordination
4.1	1	Researchers are hard to reach and/or too busy	2	3	The team will keep events concise. The team will shift the communication strategy to offer more tailored content via social media campaigns.	Coordination
4.1	2	Inability to reach new users and wider research community	2	2	The team will keep track of communication output and clear communication strategy	Low Demand
4.1	3	Project management is increasingly complex with multiple large projects run in parallel	3	2	Project management and reporting are aligned as much as possible.	Coordination
4.2	1	Not enough staffing capacity to teach courses	2	2	Active collaboration with key stakeholders such as EUR, UU, and UvA to ensure alignment and cooperation with existing graduate programs	Staffing
4.2	2	Demand for courses is too high	2	2	The task team will scale up events, and when needed, it will assist in coordinating 'train the trainer' events with ODISSEI partners.	High Demand
4.2	3	Demand for training is too low	2	3	The task team will work with the Coordination task (4.1) to increase ODISSEI's visibility. Integration in SICSS	Low Demand
4.3	1	Not obtaining appropriate time investments from researchers working with the SoDa team	1	3	Selection of researchers based on time commitment	Coordination
4.3	2	Not reaching the non-academic researchers (e.g. planbureaus)	3	1	Organising dedicated meetings with planbureaus, to discuss the needs	Coordination
4.3	3	Not being able to keep the team's knowledge state of the art	3	2	Collaboration with UU Information & Technology Services (ITS) and NLeSC; collaboration with experts in our network	Staffing
4.3	4	The team not being able to cover the wide range of required skills	1	3	Collaboration with the UU ITS team, network of experts in the UU focus area and NLeSC.	Staffing
4.3	5	Insufficient uptake of the ELSI desk support	3	1	Closer collaboration with ethics committees within universities	Coordination
4.3	6	Difficult to set up and fill position at VU to work on FAIR Expertise Hub	2	2	Conversations with people at Social Sciences faculty at VU	Staffing

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ANNEX I

Annex I – Budgeted Revenue & Expenditure for 2026 - SSHOC-NL (2024 and 2025 included as reference) [€k]

ODISSEI Tasks	Stream	SSHOC-NL Tasks	2025	2026
CBS	Data Facility	1.3	296	109
Portal	Data Facility	4.1; 4.2; 4.3	465	477
OSSC	Data Facility			
SANE	Data Facility	1.1	427	268
Data Collection	Observatory	2.2	426	223
Online Panels	Observatory	2.1	250	250
Netherlands Media	Observatory			
Data Donation	Laboratory	1.2	191	141
Mass Online Experi	Laboratory	3.3	170	173
Large Network Tool	Laboratory	3.2	228	233
Coordination	Hub	5.3	453	460
Education	Hub	5.2	184	187
Support	Hub	5.1	251	255
CLARIAH		2.3; 3.1	622	989
Total			3963	3766

ANNEX II

Annex II – Budgeted Revenue & Expenditure for 2026 - Macroscope[€k]

ODISSEI Tasks	Stream	Macroscope Tasks	2026
CBS	Data Facility	1.3	378
Portal	Data Facility	1.1	352
OSSC	Data Facility	1.2	411
SANE	Data Facility		
Data Collection	Observatory	2.1	406
Online Panels	Observatory	2.2	674
Netherlands Media	Observatory	2.3, 3.2 (without UL)	505
Data Donation	Laboratory	3.3	245
Mass Online Experi	Laboratory		
Large Network Tool	Laboratory	3.2 (only UL)	127
Coordination	Hub	4.1	332
Education	Hub	4.3	297
Support	Hub	4.2	114
CLARIAH		3.1	437
Total			4277

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